

Curbing Examination Malpractices through Principals' Management Strategies in Public Secondary Schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State

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Abstract

This research focused on Management Strategies adopted by Principals for Curbing Examination Malpractice in Secondary Schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State. The study employed a survey research design. The population of the study was twenty-nine Principals in the 29 public secondary schools in Awka north L.G.A. the entire population of was sampled for the study. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to get information from 29 respondents selected. The tool used for data analysis was mean statistics. Based on the analysis it was observed among others that moral education management strategies has a lot of influence in curbing examination malpractice among secondary schools students in Awka north L.G.A of Anambra state. Accordingly, it was recommended among others that government should institute a supervision team that will frequently visit and supervise secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State during uniform examination as a way of assisting school heads in curbing examination malpractice.

Keywords: Examination, Examination malpractice, management strategies

Introduction

Unarguably, the development and progress of any society depends largely on education. Educational efforts deliberately chosen to influence and assist children with the aim of improving knowledge, physical and morals that can gradually prepare the child to achieve the highest goals in life. Education at all levels and in all its forms, constitutes a vital tool for

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147

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addressing virtually all global problems. Education is not only an end in itself. It is a key instrument for bringing about changes in knowledge, values, behaviours and life styles which is required to achieve sustainability and stability within and among countries (Bajaj and Chiv, 2023).

However, one of the major problems confronting educational institutions especially secondary school in Nigeria is examination malpractice. The West African Examinations Council cited in Ezeudu (2021) referred to examination malpractice as an irregular behaviour exhibited by candidates or officials charged with the responsibility of conducting examination, in or outside the examination hall, before, during or after such examination. Examination malpractice is any illegal act committed by a student single handedly or in a collaboration with others; like fellow students, parents, teachers, supervisors, invigilators, printers and anybody or group of people before, during or after examination in order to obtain undeserved marks or grades. Similarly, Shonekan (2016) stated that examination malpractice is an act of omission or commission that contravenes those West African Examination Councils rules and regulations to the extent of undermining the validity and reliability of the test and ultimately the integrity of the certificate issued by the council.

In this vein, Anzene (2024) ranked examination malpractice high among the factors militating against the attainment of the objectives of schooling. There are various forms of examination malpractice. Anzene went further to identified the common malpractices committed in examinations in Nigeria as leakage of question papers, copying, changing of answer books, impersonation, misconduct in examination centres, approaching invigilators/examiner, making false entries in award list/examination registers and issuing fake certificates/degrees. Other forms of examination malpractice are bringing books or cribs into the exam hall, insulting or assaulting of supervisor or invigilator, replacement of answer scripts with another one during or after the examination, written on handkerchief/thighs, hooligans gaining entry into the examination hall

by force when examination is in progress, relaxation of vigilance by invigilators, talking, dictation of answers to students etc.

Whatever form examination malpractice manifest, their consequences on the educational system tend to be grave and varied. Examination malpractice is largely responsible for the anarchy in the disciplinary tone of the school system in Nigeria today. Akanni and Odofin (2020) observed that examination malpractice has risen up to about 51.58%. Omemu (2015) further stated that truancy, violence, cultism and drug abuse, disrespect, disobedience, absenteeism, dishonesty, laziness, poor reading culture, extortion etc have all linked to the rate at which examination malpractices is carried out in school. Examination malpractice also accounts for a large number of dropouts and from the secondary level of education bribery and immorality in schools.

Principals through some management strategies can help mitigate this ugly trend that is fast becoming a tradition in secondary schools in north local government area of Anambra State. Onyibe, Uma & Ibina, (2015) posit that there are a number of management strategies for curbing examination malpractice namely, moral education, stiff punishment and adult literacy.

Efforts geared towards curbing this problem seem to have yielded no dividends; hence the urgent need to adopt the strategy of moral Education. This is so because; examination malpractice is a reflection of the moral decadence in the society. Moral education is essential for bringing up morally sound children (Mathieson & McCulloch, 2015). Good character is required for a crime-free society to be instilled in the people at an early stage. Moral education ensures that the people know what is good, desire what is good; and do what is good. This attitude should be instilled in the youth right from the primary schools to secondary schools. Values such as peace, honesty, forthrightness and dedication; diligence are cherished and aspired by the world all over. Such values are the sustaining forces of human society and progress. What children and youths learn is inter woven into the fabric of the society. So, positive values should be passed on to the school children. Another strategy is stiff punishment on the culprits to serve as deterrent.

Stiff punishment such as paying fine, imprisonment as stipulated in the examination malpractice decree and also expelling the student(s) among others should be strictly adhered to. This will make students to shun examination malpractice because of the fear of the punishment (Mahadeo, 2014), apart from punishment, principals can still adopt the option of counselling.

Counselling is the process involved in directing and guiding the students in choosing a field of study where he can perform better, by so doing it will be useless to cheat. However, the pressing issue at hand is how to find a lasting solution to any ugly incidence that may arise by introducing counselling strategies. Omorgie (2016) advocated the need to strategies that appeal to the conscience of the students in curbing examination malpractice. These include strategies such as guidance and counselling. Guidance and counselling are one of the educational support services provided in schools to help students manage their psychosocial and learning problems. Iwuama (2015) sees counselling as a learning process in which individuals learn about themselves, their interpersonal relations and behaviours that advance their personal development. Counselling from this point of view entails a change in behaviour after a person must have X-rayed himself, his interaction patterns with other people and his general way of life. Such self-examination enables him to coin for himself the best way of conducting himself in the most socially acceptable manner. He learns about himself, other persons and his environment and uses such knowledge to develop the right attitudes and values within his social milieu. It is a method of helping the individual's positive strengths for development and by concentrating on the individual's personality behavioural and emotional assets that could be mobilized.

From the foregoing, it is logical to argue the examination malpractice pose a great threat to the survival and sustainability of quality education in Nigeria in general and in Awka North Local Government Area in particular. It is therefore extremely important to seek for solutions that would reduce this devastating cankerworm thereby assuring the validity and reliability of examination in Awka North Local Government Area. The study is therefore motivated by the need to ascertain the influence of management strategies adopted by the principals of various

secondary schools so as to reduce examination malpractice in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Examination in secondary schools should be true judgment by standard. With it, one can determine the true level of performance in each subject by students as well as their achievement standing from one level of class to the other. For a long time, particularly in the last two decades examination malpractice has made it impossible for examination at any level in some secondary school in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State to be a true test of students' knowledge. Many have graduated with very good results but could neither construct a simple letter nor express themselves effectively. A good number have acquired little or no skills taught at that level. The government and the citizens who were educated before this new trend find it very worrisome. If the situation is not arrested, Nigeria will definitely regress educationally while the rest of the world progress steadily. This would spell doom for younger generation. Therefore, it is necessary that our examination should be free from malpractice. Practices ranging from sorting, exam leakage and parents' collaboration with the teachers have become common features of examinations in secondary schools in Awka north. The researcher hopes that principals management strategies can help curb examination malpractice in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State, hence this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the management strategies adopted by principals for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. Principals' moral education management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State.

2. Principals' Stiff punishment management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State
3. Principals' counselling management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of principals' moral education management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State?
2. What is the influence of principals' counselling management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State?
3. What is the influence of principals' stiff punishment management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State?

Methods

The research design used for this study was survey research design. The target population of the study comprises of 29 principals of the 29 public secondary schools in Awka North LGA of Anambra State. All the 29 principals of the schools in the study area were selected. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire which was designed and developed

by the researcher. The instrument is titled; Questionnaire on management strategies adopted by principals for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Educational Management and Policy and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation unit of Educational Foundations department (it was a content validation), all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The instrument was structured on four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly Disagreed (SD), and Disagreed (D). They were weighed on 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The questionnaire was administered all the principals in the twenty-nine secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area by the researcher and two research assistants. Distribution and collection of the questionnaire was made on the spot through the aid of the research assistants to reduce incident of loss of questionnaire. Out of Twenty-nine (29) administered, twenty-seven were successfully retrieved which serve as 98% return rate. The responses of each item of the research questions were tallied and weighted using four (4) point rating scale. The total weighted frequencies were used to determine the mean scores of each item. Mean scores from 2.50 was considered accepted while mean score below 2.50 was considered rejected. The mean was used to analyse the research questions posed for the study.

Results

Research Question One: what is the influence of the principal's moral education management strategies for curbing examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean rating on principal’s moral education Management Strategies curb examination malpractice in secondary schools.

S/N	Items	Mean	Remark
1.	Imbibe the consciousness of the consequences of malpractice in education in the students’ academic growth.	2.79	Agreed
2.	Instil the drive for good conduct among the students hence they refrain from examination malpractice.	2.59	Disagreed
3.	Makes each student to become a watchdog on one another as to ensure the practice of good moral and shun exam malpractice	2.43	Disagreed
4.	Encourages the students to put more effort in learning since their good conscience will be questioned during examination.	3.0	Agreed
Grand Mean		2.70	Agreed

In table 1 above, three out of all the items obtained mean rating above the criterion of 2.50 and above indicating agreed to items. And item two (Principal's morals education management strategy instils the drive for good conduct among the students hence they refrain from examination malpractice) in the table was disagreed with mean rating below 2.50. The mean of mean also obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50 and above, showing that majority of the items listed on Principal's moral education management strategies in secondary schools in Awka North LGA of Anambra State curb examination malpractice among students. This finding is in agreement with the study of Ikeogu (2016) who observed that in schools, moral issues are part and parcel of school life and are important tool for teachers and principals to

utilise in addressing social vices such as examination malpractice. The concurrence of the present finding and that of Ikeogu (2016) may have been as a result of the fact that the two studies were conducted in the same state governed by the same government policy.

Research Question Two: what is the influence of the principal stiff management strategies curb examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean rating on Principal's stiff management strategies curb examination malpractice in Secondary Schools

S/N	Items	Mean	Remark
9.	Instil fear among the students which make them abstain from cheating during examination.	2.90	Agreed
10	Ignites a sense of responsibilities among students which relatively give no ground for examination malpractice.	2.40	Disagreed
11.	Serves as a forewarning to the students who will be forced to observe that cheating in exam will be met with severe punishment.	3.55	Agreed
12	Principal's threat to publicly shame any student caught in examination malpractice will compel students to completely abstain from examination malpractice	2.65	Agreed
Grand Mean		2.87	Agreed

In table 2 above, three out of four of all the items obtained mean rating above the criterion of 2.50 and above indicating agreed to items. And item ten (Principal's stiff management strategy ignites a sense of responsibilities among students which relatively give no ground for examination malpractice) in the table was disagreed with mean rating below 2.50. The mean of mean also obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50 and above, showing that majority of the items listed on Principal stiff management strategies in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State curbs malpractices in examination among students. The findings of the study based on the mean shows that all the above items on

Principal stiff management strategies curb examination malpractice among students in secondary schools in Awka North LGA of Anambra State. The finding of the present study corroborates the finding of (Okoye, 2024) who pointed out that the school administrator is vested with the responsibility of ensuring strict discipline among the students especially in cases of malpractices in examinations as this will go a long way in curbing the incidence of examination malpractice. Similarity in time lag and research method may have accounted for the agreement of the two studies.

Research Question Three: what is the influence of the principals counselling management strategies curb examination malpractice in secondary schools in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State?

Table 3: Mean rating on Principals counselling management strategies curb examination malpractice in secondary Schools.

S/N		Mean	Remark
5	Through counselling management strategy of principal's, students are directed to choose subjects that suit them better and will make them not to cheat to pass exams.	2.91	Agreed
6	Counselling management strategy of principals enables the students to express themselves and got help in areas they really need It; hence, they do not cheat in exams.	3.45	Agreed
7.	Counselling management strategy of principals breaches the gap between the students and the school staff, thereby boosting the confidence of the students and stifling every space for exam malpractice.	2.43	Disagreed
8.	Counselling management strategy of Principals prevents the students from developing wrong attitude from external influence and enhances their Interest in passing without cheating in exams.	3.0	Agreed
Grand Mean		2.94	Agreed

In table 3 above, three of all the items obtained mean rating above the criterion of 2.50 and above indicating agreed to items. And item seven (Counselling management strategy of principals

breaches the gap between the students and the school staff, thereby boosting the confidence of the students and stifling every space for exam malpractice) in the table was disagreed with mean rating below 2.50. The mean of mean also obtained mean rating above the criterion mean of 2.50 and above, showing that majority of the items listed on principals counselling management strategies in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State fosters malpractice-free examination among secondary school students. The findings of the study based on the mean shows that all the above items on Principals counselling management strategies in Awka North Local Government Area of Anambra State curb examination malpractice among secondary school students. This finding confirms the position of (Renuka 2023) who pointed out that one of the major reasons for the counselling sessions in schools, aside from helping them cope, is to also ensure that vices such as examination malpractices are reduced to the barest minimum.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that moral education, stiff punishment and counselling are management strategies that principals can adopt to curb examination malpractice strategies among secondary school students in Awka North Local Government of Anambra State.

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